

Conservation of Energy as the Remover of Bias in an Ideal Gas?

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution associated with an ideal gas is often derived by considering the total energy of the gas being distributed over N particles such that any distribution set has the same probability. This is taken as a fundamental a priori assumption, it seems, from which one may write an expression for the number of distributions sets. Taking the \ln of this number and maximizing by variation of $n(e_i)$ subject to an average energy constraint yields the MB distribution.

Alternatively, one may consider conservation of energy in two body collisions: $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ together with time reversal: $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ and obtain the MB distribution. In this approach it seems as if there are two independent conditions which are then considered to be in fact the same, from which follows the MB distribution.

Here, we define time reversal through $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$, ((1)) but relax the condition of conservation of kinetic energy of a particle. This suggests that there must be an extra energy pool, but for equilibrium, this pool must neither grow nor decrease. Thus, one must impose a rule which suggests a given e_i, e_j set either takes energy from the pool or releases it depending on the sum of $e_k + e_l$. If $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$, then no energy is taken or released, but this means that $f(e_i)f(e_j) = \text{function}(e_i + e_j)$ proportional to number power $(e_i + e_j)$. In other words, there is no bias involved in distributing $E = e_i + e_j$ to any other set e_k, e_l such that $e_k + e_l = E$. If this is the case, then one cannot have time reversal for the case in which $e_i + e_j \neq e_k + e_l$ and at the same allow for time reversal for the equality case.

In order to allow for exothermic or endothermic reactions with time reversal it seems one must give up the notion of $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ being possible. In other words, one must assume that a reaction must either be exothermic or endothermic. In such a case, ((1)) must hold for $e_i + e_j > e_k + e_l$ as well as for $e_i + e_j < e_k + e_l$. In particular, for the latter case, e_{k1}, e_{l1} and e_{k2}, e_{l2} have the same product probabilities as do any two sets multiplied together. This seems to imply that one must have $f(e_i)$ the same for any e_i . Then $\sum_i e_i \text{ constant} = E_{\text{total}}$, ((2)) where E_{total} is the average total kinetic energy, but there is also a constant pool energy as well. ((2)), however, restricts the e_i that are possible. For example, if one has N particles, then the probability for e_i must be the same for all e_i , but this is not possible. Thus, by contradiction, one must reject the exothermic or endothermic only scenario and use time reversal with energy conservation in reactions if one wishes to have a minimal informational equilibrium.. We suggest that a key to allowing for all e_i sets such that $\sum e_i = E_{\text{total}}$ with equal probability is directly linked to conservation of energy in a reaction.

Maximization of Entropy Subject to an Energy Constraint in an Ideal Gas

A traditional approach of deriving the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for an ideal gas is based on the a priori assumption that all distributions of a total energy E among N particles has the same probability. From this assumption, the number of arrangements is:

$$N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \quad ((1))$$

Taking the \ln of ((1)), using Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n)$ and maximizing ((1)) (varying with respect to $n(e_i)$) subject to the constraint $\sum_i n(e_i)/N$ yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann probability: $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where T is temperature and C a normalization constant (function of T).

In this derivation, the a priori assumption of equal probabilities for any distribution of E among N particles is the key idea. There is no focus on the specific interactions which occur or whether they are elastic because all one requires is that E_{total} remain constant, where E_{total} is the sum of kinetic energies of the particles in a nonrelativistic treatment.

Collision Approach

Another approach to calculation the MB distribution is to consider two body elastic collisions, together with time reversal and write:

$$E_i + e_j = e_k + e_l \quad ((2a))$$

$$f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l) \quad ((2b))$$

((2a)) demonstrates energy conservation in a collision and ((2b)), time reversal. If one suggests that the two equations are in fact the same, then: $\ln(f(e_i)) = -\text{constant } e_i$ and one obtains the MB distribution.

Scenario of Non-Elastic Collisions

We try to consider the case of time reversal with non-energy conservation. First, however, we consider $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ if $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. In such a case, $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_i + e_j)$ meaning that any distribution of $E = e_i + e_j$ yields the same probability product. This is in keeping with the a priori assumption of equal probability energy distributions of E_{total}/N and represents minimal information.

To try to alter this result, one might allow for some conservation of energy cases $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$, but disallow others based on some kind of rule. This, however, introduces extra information into the problem and so cannot be the solution based on the least amount of information.

Our next consideration is one which does not allow for any elastic collisions, but insists that physically (for some reason) an interaction should be either endothermic or exothermic. In such a case, there must be an E_{total} representing kinetic energy and a fixed pool energy which supplies or receives extra energy. For equilibrium, these must be constant values.

In such a case, for time reversal one still has ((2b))

$$f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l) \quad ((3)), \text{ but } ((2a)) \text{ no longer holds.}$$

This means that any reaction may occur with equal probability (for minimal information) and suggests that:

$$f(e_i) = \text{constant} \quad ((4)) \text{ for a minimal informational equilibrium system}$$

The problem with this scenario is that in forming:

$E_{\text{total}} = \sum_i e_i f(e_i)$ where $f(e_i) = \text{constant}$ ((5)), ((5)) cannot be satisfied.

For example, if one considers $f(E/2) = 1/2$ for two particles with the N-2 rest having $e_i = 0$, then for $f(E/3) = 1/3$ for three particles with the N-3 rest having $e_i = 0$, then one has already broken the condition ((4)). Thus, it seems one cannot consider an exothermic-endothermic scenario and needs to resort to conservation of energy in order to have a minimal informational system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that the traditional maximization of entropy subject to an average energy constraint for the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor does not focus on the specific interactions or whether they involve conservation of energy. An alternative approach is to combine conservation of energy in 2-body collisions with $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ (time reversal). One then argues that these two equations are equivalent.

In this note, we try to consider the case of time reversal for only exothermic or endothermic collisions and argue that if one wishes to have a minimal informational equilibrium system one must have elastic collisions. Thus, the choice of elastic collisions is key to a minimal informational equilibrium system. We investigate this because $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ is often introduced as an a priori condition without an explanation given for it being linked to minimal information.